

ISSUES OF ENSURING INVESTMENT POLICY PARTICIPATION IN UZBEKISTAN

U.Sh. Olimjonova

Namangan State University, master's student

Abstract: *This article focuses on the activities of Uzbekistan's investment policy and various issues related to it.*

Key words: *Investment policy, intellectual capital, resources, investment portfolio, financial project.*

Introduction

Since the first years of independence, the investment policy implemented in Uzbekistan has supported the priority areas for ensuring the independence of fuel, energy and grain, implementing structural changes in the economy, increasing the export potential and increasing the production of import-substituting products. - support, open door policy to attract foreign investments was focused on. The investment policy is based on the following principles:

- selective support of the most important sectors and areas of activity based on the established state priorities;
- sufficient support for socially important sectors (health, education, culture, etc.) in order to improve the standard of living of the population, extend their life, prevent sharp social stratification, and ensure the activation of consumer demand;
- attraction of foreign investments to priority areas on the basis of mutual benefit;
- redistribution of potential investment resources from trade and money market to industry;
- increasing intellectual capital and scientific and technical potential due to the concentration of production capital by supporting scientific research,

experimental design work, buying licenses for new techniques from abroad, forming large corporations capable of maintaining large laboratories;

- supporting investment projects aimed at deep processing of agricultural products and mineral resources and bringing them to the level of competitiveness in the foreign market;

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- supporting investment projects aimed at deep processing of agricultural products and mineral resources and bringing them to the level of competitiveness in the foreign market;

- ensuring with investments the rapid development of production capacities designed to meet the needs of the population for food and consumer goods;

- improvement of the legal framework that regulates the interaction of the participants of investment processes. For this purpose, it is necessary to pay great attention to the support of investment projects implemented by the state in these areas. The word "project" has become widespread in economic theory and practice today. The existence of different views on the interpretation of its meaning increases the interest in studying and revealing the essence of this term. According to the experts of the Economic Development Institute of the World Bank, the project: firstly, targeted activity; secondly, the benefit always exceeds its costs; thirdly, it will have a strict limitation of limited time and resources.

Economic development manifests itself as a complex process, and progress in this area is measured by several indicators: gross domestic product, income, profit, consumption level, health, life expectancy, literacy, quality improvement, etc. can be reflected. For this reason, the project idea may not have the same meaning for all cases, and there may not be a single model form of project development and evaluation.

In turn, projects consist of a number of targeted activities representing their individual elements and indicators, a management system aimed at project implementation and achieving the intended result, etc.

According to this, it is possible to observe different definitions of its content: Project is a certain task related to certain initial data and required results (goal), which includes the method of solving it. ("Project Management Code of Knowledge", Project Management Institute, USA); Project (eng. Project) is something that is invented or planned, for example, a large enterprise (Webster's dictionary). From the point of view of a systematic approach, the project can be viewed as a process of transition from the initial state to the final result with the participation of a number of constraints and mechanisms.

It is clear to all of us that today in Uzbekistan, state programs that require large investments are being implemented, and this includes the provision of

housing and their construction in rural areas, the development of industry, the production of food products for the population, transport and communication. system development and other (fuel and energy, mechanical engineering, road construction and repair, localization, etc.) state programs can be cited as examples. The concept of "investment project" is interpreted in 2 different ways:

1) as a work, activity, measure that implies the implementation of some complex of actions that ensures the achievement of certain goals (obtaining certain results);

2) as a system of organizational-legal, technical, accounting and financial documents necessary for the implementation of certain actions and activities. The terms "business event", work "summary of work", "project" are close to the content of the first case. The implementation of the project takes place in a certain internal dynamic and surrounded by the external environment and has a certain impact on it. At the same time, in construction projects, it is necessary to be able to determine and calculate all types of statistical and dynamic loads that fall on the construction of the device, as well as in a larger project, all physical, economic, social factors that may affect the project and its environment. , financial organization, etc. it is important to identify and take into account the factors, under certain conditions, each of these factors can become dangerous for the project and lead to its destruction.

The relationship between the project and the environment can be considered as an example of a product development project for an enterprise that produces a certain product. Normal, long-term activity of the organization serves as the basis for the emergence of demand in the conditions of changes and renewal. This, in turn, leads to the emergence of a project. When the project actually starts, it starts to develop independently. During the implementation of the project, its participants focus on fulfilling their tasks. During the implementation of the project, the normal life of the enterprise in production, sales and management will continue. The same

applies to the environment of the project. Here, too, there are changes that affect the project through the enterprise. The project cannot be separated from the existing conditions and their development. Therefore, it is necessary to take into account the immediate environment of the project (that is, the enterprise itself) and the environment (that is, the environment of the enterprise) in advance. The following table shows the composition of capital investments (foreign investments and loans) in Uzbekistan by sources of financing.

Table 1. Structure of capital investments in Uzbekistan by sources of financing (foreign investments and loans)¹

Territories	2000	2001	2002	2003	2004	2005	2006	2007	2008	2009	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021
Republic of Uzbekistan	23,2	28,0	20,1	24,2	25,1	21,7	18,5	24,5	30,0	32,4	26,4	19,8	19,0	18,1	18,5	18,5	20,7	23,8	24,3	43,6	42,7	42,3
Republic of Karakalpakstan	6,6	12,1	10,3	11,7	29,3	23,4	21,6	5,0	5,8	16,8	12,6	13,8	28,7	30,5	47,4	48,2	44,6	10,0	23,7	36,9	38,9	37,4
Andijan	4,5	27,4	18,6	42,8	12,8	19,6	13,2	9,5	14,6	2,7	8,2	6,3	7,5	5,2	6,2	4,4	4,9	7,2	14,8	39,6	36,3	45,6
Bukhara	10,5	8,5	11,6	8,0	20,2	10,8	8,5	56,8	53,7	78,0	63,2	58,2	50,4	50,6	45,1	35,9	52,4	71,0	44,0	53,9	48,2	58,5
Jizzakh	28,9	28,2	2,9	3,1	25,2	6,2	14,4	10,4	14,0	8,1	7,6	6,3	3,1	2,8	5,9	2,9	7,3	10,8	8,7	48,8	61,9	44,5
Kashkadarya	31,3	37,3	23,9	16,2	16,3	11,8	17,5	26,7	45,5	37,4	26,5	19,3	23,2	22,8	19,5	17,6	27,5	18,0	51,1	70,3	69,3	53,6
Navoi	20,3	42,2	3,3	28,9	6,2	23,5	1,7	18,1	12,8	3,3	25,2	9,5	24,0	22,7	10,3	3,0	5,1	24,2	34,0	39,9	67,8	61,3
Namangan	2,3	17,8	16,9	13,8	11,3	12,3	9,3	6,6	18,9	4,3	4,7	4,2	3,2	6,8	16,4	21,9	22,6	31,6	33,5	45,8	37,2	29,8
Samarqand	13,3	13,5	9,9	20,6	14,3	17,7	12,8	9,7	11,4	9,6	3,2	4,2	3,6	4,0	3,4	4,0	2,2	2,8	4,7	27,8	27,0	34,9
Surkhondarya	4,9	2,9	1,6	14,4	11,4	6,3	5,9	11,1	26,5	11,6	5,2	7,2	11,0	12,0	12,2	10,4	9,8	11,5	21,4	66,3	60,1	45,2
Syrdarya	21,7	22,6	4,5	17,3	22,5	17,6	21,0	10,8	10,4	14,7	9,6	4,7	2,6	9,6	9,6	10,8	7,7	4,6	9,6	44,8	48,7	59,8
Tashkent	31,1	23,5	18,7	17,6	23,8	16,6	13,8	11,4	19,8	12,9	16,4	16,6	16,1	10,7	10,9	15,3	13,7	12,0	9,6	26,0	26,7	34,3
Fergana	27,3	40,3	45,4	27,8	9,3	10,1	12,9	10,4	24,4	20,4	12,3	15,4	11,1	11,8	8,7	7,6	8,9	5,8	19,4	42,7	41,3	39,1
Khorezm	9,5	23,3	41,6	18,1	18,9	15,1	30,4	21,2	9,7	5,0	9,8	11,3	9,5	4,8	7,4	2,7	5,8	6,8	8,5	42,5	32,0	33,5
Tashkent city	34,2	29,2	20,1	41,0	45,1	42,3	38,6	41,3	35,7	32,0	39,5	28,8	19,6	17,7	13,1	13,0	16,4	18,1	15,1	36,7	29,9	37,3

Based on the above table, the highest growth results in the last decade were Andijan region, from 8.2 to 45.6, Jizzakh region from 7.6 to 44.5, Kashkadarya region from 26.5 to 53.6, Sirdarya region from 9.6 we can see that it has increased from 59.8. In conclusion, it can be said that we offer the following suggestions for improving the efficiency of foreign investments in our country:

- formation of software platforms aimed at state insurance of investors' investments, assessment of existing conditions and possibilities of attracting foreign investments in the regions;
- improvement of the regulatory framework for attracting investments to the regions and providing tax preferences for their development, wide incentives for increasing the share of tax revenues remaining in the region;

¹ stat.uz prepared by the author based on his information

- it is appropriate to implement issues such as reconstruction of the internal structure of industrial sectors, production of industrial products, and ensuring the practical implementation of the tasks of directing advanced technologies to the preparation of high-quality industrial goods.

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